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ABSTRACT

This report describes the extent of ongoing proposed training activities on particle accelerators in Europe, as well as their coordination and interaction.

The data used for the report is collected by carrying out a web-based survey. In total, 90 institutes and companies from 21 countries have participated in the ARIES survey on “Training in Accelerator Science”. Out of 90 responders, 50 responders were universities, 28 responders were national and international laboratories and 12 were companies.

The report presents the provision of training, trainee numbers, training time, training subjects of the responding institutes, including training needs of companies. Coordination of training activities - accelerator schools, developments of MOOCs and use of facilities – is also outlined.

ARIES Consortium, 2020

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

- In total, 90 institutes and companies from 21 countries completed the ARIES survey on “Training in Accelerator Science”. Out of 90 responders, 50 were universities, 28 were national and international laboratories, and 12 were companies. All European countries with significant accelerator training activities have responded to the survey. We can assume that this gives a quite complete picture of the status of accelerator training in Europe.
- Training in some aspect of accelerators is provided by 39 universities (78%), by 25 out of 28 national and international laboratories (89%), and by 5 out of 12 companies (41%).
- Out of the responding institutes, 55 (61%) send their people to attend accelerator schools which provide centralised training and 26 (29%) send their people to provide training at the accelerator schools, indicating a good level of collaboration.
- In 2018, 1220 students received training in accelerator science. Out of which 23% were undergraduates, 32% Master students, 19% PhD students, 5% post-doctoral fellows, 10% staff, and 10% other students. Most of training is provided at Master student level, while only a small fraction of training is provided to staff of accelerator laboratories.
- 42 institutes reported a total formal training time of 6,555 hours per year, with an average of 156 hours per institute per year. 18% of training time went to undergraduates, 27% to master’s students, 27% to PhD students, 18% to staff and 5% to post-doctoral fellows.
- The majority of the trainees receive training in 5 areas: particle sources, accelerating structures, magnets, beam dynamics and beam instrumentation and control. More than 50% of the responding institutes offer training in one of these 5 areas.
- 22% of institutes that train undergraduates offer formal examinations on course work; the corresponding figure for master’s students is 37%, and for PhD students is 18%.
- 18% of institutes participate in ECTS for undergraduates, the corresponding figure for master’s students is 24% and that for PhD students is 18%.
- The most attended international schools are the CERN Accelerator Schools (CAS), the Joint Universities Accelerator School (JUAS), the U.S. Particle Accelerator Schools (USPAS) and the Linear Collider School.
- Five MOOCS (massive open online course) are reported. The MOOC duration varies from 20 hours to 100 hours. It has been developed by co-ordination between different institutes.
- 73 institutes reported use of national and/or international accelerator facilities as part of their training programme. The most-used facility is CERN. More than 10 institutes train their people are ESS, Fermilab, DESY, SLAC, GSI, national or regional light sources, showing a good level of coordination.
- 4 universities and 1 company have reported past training activities that have been discontinued, after a duration between 4 and 38 years.
- 8 institutes have planned future training activities, including doctoral programs on accelerator science, and master programs in accelerator science.
- 81% of the companies have expressed need for additional training, even though all the companies send their personnel to the accelerator schools.

1. Introduction

A survey of the provision of training in accelerator science was performed between November 2019 and March 2020. Approximately 140 institutes in 23 countries were contacted. A total of 90 institutes from 21 countries have responded to the survey. The responses were from 50 universities, 28 National- International laboratories and 12 companies (Figure 1.1). The institutes and respective countries are listed in APPENDIX 1.

A web-based survey was conducted, using a survey monkey tool. A representative of each institute was requested to provide responses to straightforward questions concerning training in accelerator science at her/his institute. Information was requested about the institute and its staff, whether training is provided. The details of any training and the recipients of the training were also requested. A text version of the survey is given in APPENDIX 2.

A similar “Education and Training Survey” was carried out in 2012 by the TIARA project, based on input from 88 institutes in 13 countries. This resulted in the “Needs for Accelerator Scientists Report” (<http://cds.cern.ch/record/1521336/files/>), for which universities, National-international laboratories and companies were contacted.

The ARIES survey questions were designed to map out the TIARA survey, so as to compare the accelerator training provision between the two survey periods 2005-2012 and 2013-2019.

Figure 1.1: Number of responding institutes vs institute type.

In each country the survey was targeted primarily at those institutes known to be engaged in accelerator science activities, but an attempt was made also to advertise the survey more widely so as to allow the potential for capturing a more complete picture. The 90 Institutes that responded to the survey (64% of the total contacted) cover almost all those providing accelerator training in Europe, and a large majority of those requiring training.

2. Participation in the Survey

The country wise distribution of the number of scientific institutes that have responded to the survey is shown in Figure 2.1. They comprise universities, national and international laboratories. The red dash shows the number of institutes contacted and the blue column shows the number of institutes that responded. The wider response was from UK, where 18 replied out of 19 contacted. In total, 78 institutes from 21 countries responded to the survey for a response rate of 61%.

Figure 2.1: Total number of responses from scientific institutes by country (blue). For each country, the number of institutes contacted is indicated by a red dash.

The survey was also sent to 13 companies in 10 countries (see Figure 2.2). Here as well the red dash shows the number of companies contacted and the blue column shows the number of companies that responded. In total, 12 companies from 12 countries have responded to the survey, for a response rate of 92%, much larger than for scientific institutes.

Figure 2.2: Total number of responses from companies by country (blue). For each country, the number of companies contacted is indicated by the red dash.

3. Institutes' Provision of Training

Out of the 90 responding institutes and companies, 69 are engaged in accelerator training of some sort (Figure 3.1). The blue column denotes the number of institutes providing training in accelerators, whereas the red column denotes the number of institutes that don't provide training in accelerators.

The large majority of the Universities replying to the survey (39/50, 78%) provide some training in accelerator, as well as most of the national/international laboratories (25/28, 89%). Instead, only 41% of the companies (5/12) provide some sort of training in accelerator science.

Figure 3.1: The number of universities, national / international laboratories and companies that offer training is shown by blue column and those who don't offer training is shown by red column

The country-wise distribution of the universities and national /international laboratories that provide training in some aspect of accelerator is shown in Figure 3.2.

It is interesting to observe that practically all UK Universities and Laboratories provide some sort of accelerator training (17 out of 18). Accelerator training is very well present in Europe, provided in 17 different countries. The largest number of institutions is present in the UK (17), followed by Germany (10), and Italy (7).

Figure 3.2: The number of universities and national / international laboratories that offer training in accelerator science is shown by green column and those who don't offer training is shown by red column

The country-wise distribution of the companies that provide training in some aspect of accelerator is shown in Figure 3.3. Only few companies provide training, in Belgium, Germany, Italy, Slovenia and Sweden.

Figure 3.3: The number of companies that offer training in accelerator science is shown by green column and those who don't offer training is shown by red column

The accelerator training can be provided in different ways like providing formal lectures, hands on training at the institute / site, providing internal courses etc. Figure 3.4 lists different training provisions in accelerator science used by universities, laboratories and companies. The training provisions by universities are shown by blue column bar, that by laboratories are shown by red column bar and that by companies are shown by green column bar.

As expected, Universities provide a large and diversified amount of training on accelerators. Out of the responding Universities, 68% provide formal lectures, 52% provide hands on training at their campus or at site, 40% provide internal courses, 98% send their people to attend the accelerator schools, 58% send people to attend conferences or workshops, 40% provide seminars or on-line seminars, 1% are using MOOC (Massive Online Open Course) for training, 6% have contributed to MOOC development, and no one uses online training material. On top, 16% offer other methods of training that include buying formal courses from nearby universities, use of thesis (bachelor's, Master's or PhD), developing training networks, involving students in accelerator projects, etc.

Laboratories provide training mainly by attendance to workshops or conferences (88%) and by sending people to accelerator schools (96%).

While the preferred training for companies is sending people to accelerator schools (100%), the second most used training tool is using online material (75%), an approach exclusively used by companies.

Figure 3.4: Percentage of universities, laboratories and companies following different training provisions

More than 90% of the responding institutes sent their personnel to accelerator schools (Figure 3.4). The percentage is very high in almost all countries (Figure 3.5), apart from Spain, France, Russia and Malta where only 50% or less of the institutes makes use of this training option.

Training opportunities are well distributed between the different categories of trainees (undergraduate, master’s, PhD, postdoctoral fellow, staff) for each country, as shown in Figure 3.6. Provision of training is most common at the master’s and PhD level, though many institutes provide training at the undergraduate level, as well as to postdoctoral fellows and staff. Overall, 31% of institutes train undergraduates, 56% master’s students, 54% PhD students, 23% post-doctoral fellows and 32% to staff and 31% to other students.

Figure 3.5: The percentage of responding institutes in each country that send people for training to accelerator schools (blue), and that provide training at accelerator schools and workshops (yellow).

Figure 3.6: The percentage of responding institutes in each country that currently offer training to each category of trainee.

4. Trainee Numbers

Integrated over all institutions, the number of people receiving any training in accelerator science is shown, by trainee type, in Figure 4.1: The total number of accelerator science trainees, by trainee type. Data are shown for the academic year 2019 (green), 2018 (red) and the average over the 5 years 2013-2017 (blue). Taking 2018 as a reference, a total of 1,255 people received some training in accelerators. This number included 273 undergraduates (23%), 393 master’s students (32%), 235 PhD students (19%), 70 postdoctoral fellows (6%), 124 staff (10%) and 119 others (10%) (Figure 4.2). The category ‘others’ includes, among others, visiting overseas students and industry employees.

The numbers did not change dramatically during the period 2013–2019. There are minor differences in the numbers of undergraduates (about + 5%), master’s students (-3%), PhD students (6%) and post-doctoral fellows (-16%), staff (+4%) that were trained between 2013 and 2019.

Figure 4.1: The total number of accelerator science trainees, by trainee type. Data are shown for the academic year 2019 (green), 2018 (red) and the average over the 5 years 2013-2017 (blue).

Figure 4.2: Relative proportions of trainee types in academic year 2018

The total number of trainees in each country is shown in Figure 4.3. The UK is the country training more people in accelerators, more than 25% of the total in Europe, followed by Germany that accounts for another 19%. Poland and France are also very active, at about 10%, followed by Finland, Switzerland and Italy.

It is interesting to compare the number of accelerator trainees per country to their overall population (Figure 4.4, for 2018). The countries with the largest share of accelerator trainees are Finland and Malta.

Figure 4.3: The total number of trainees in each country. Data are shown for the academic year 2019 (green), 2018 (red) and the average per year over the 5 years 2013-2017 (blue).

Figure 4.4: The total number of trainees in each country (for academic year 2018) normalised by the population of that country, expressed in trainees per million.

For each country, the percentage of the accelerator science population of each trainee type (for academic year 2018 as an example) is represented in Figure 4.5. A comparison between countries of the six different trainee types is shown in Figure 4.6 .

Figure 4.5: Representation of the percentage of trainees in each country (for academic year 2018) that is of each type.

Figure 4.6: For each country, the total number of trainees in each category. Data are shown for the academic year 2019 (Yellow), 2018 (blue) and the average per year over the 5 years 20013- 2017 (grey). (a) Undergraduates; (b) master’s students; (c) PhD students; (d) postdoctoral fellows; (e) staff; (f) others.

5. Formal Training Time

42 of the 78 institutes that provide training reported the number of formal training hours provided. Formal training is defined to be instructive training provided in a lecture, class or tutorial environment. The distribution of the number of formal training hours per year is shown in Figure 5.1; training hours are shown separately for the different categories of students. For any student type the amount of training varies considerably, from between a few hours to hundreds of hours, though the majority of institutions provide of order a few tens of hours of such training.

Out of the responding institutes, 4 institutes provide more than 100 hours of training to undergraduate students:

1. Stockholm University
2. Bergische Universität Wuppertal
3. Warsaw University of Technology
4. National Research Nuclear University MEPhI (Moscow)

5 institutes provide more than 100 hours of training to master's students:

5. DELTA, TU Darmstadt
6. Institut für Kernphysik der Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz
7. Bergische Universität Wuppertal
8. Warsaw University of Technology
9. National Research Nuclear University MEPhI (Moscow)

4 institutes provide more than 100 hours of training to PhD students:

10. Lancaster University
11. Oxford University
12. Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
13. National Research Nuclear University MEPhI (Moscow)

Figure 5.1: Distribution of the number of formal training hours per year provided. Data are shown for separate categories of trainee. Zeroes have not been displayed. The bin width is 10 hours.

Figure 5.2: The total number of trainees who received at least 10 hours of formal training in accelerator science, by trainee type. Data are shown for the academic year 2018 (blue), 2019 (red) and the average per year over the 5 years 2013-2017 (green).

The total number of reported formal training hours per annum currently provided is shown by country in Figure 5.3. Note that, since 36 institutes did not provide data on the number of hours, these numbers represent lower bounds, and the real total will be larger.

The total number of reported training hours by country is shown in Figure 5.4, and by category of trainee in Figure 5.5. Overall, of the 6,555 total reported training hours provided per annum, 27% are currently given to master’s students, 18% to undergraduates, 27% to PhD students, 18% to staff and 5% to post-doctoral fellows.

It appears that Germany and United Kingdom are the countries providing more formal training in accelerator science, in particular to PhD students. Finland, Poland and Italy (for master students) follow.

Figure 5.3: The total number of accelerator science formal training hours reported by institutes that offer training to each category of trainee, by country.

The distribution of the percentage of formal training time that is spent on accelerator science is shown by category of trainee in Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.6 shows the percentage of training on accelerators with respect to the overall training provided by the institution. Accelerator science typically represents a small fraction of total training time, which reflects the fact that it is often a small component of a more general training in physics and/or engineering disciplines. This is particularly evident for undergraduate, master’s and PhD students. For postdoctoral fellows and staff a noticeably higher fraction of their total training time is spent on accelerator science, reflecting the fact that they are professionals in this discipline.

Figure 5.4: Total reported formal training hours spent on accelerator science per country.

Figure 5.5: Total reported formal training hours spent on accelerator science by category of trainee.

Figure 5.6: Distribution of the percentage of formal training time that is spent on accelerator science.

6. Training Subjects

Figure 6.1.

The majority of trainees receive training in eight areas:

- Particle sources
- Accelerating structures
- Magnets
- Beam dynamics
- Beam instrumentation and control
- Laser systems for accelerators
- Cryogenics
- Radio Frequency (RF)

Figure 6.1: Number of trainees versus training area and by category of trainee.

Figure 6.2 shows the percentage of institutes that offer training in each subject area; more than 50% of institutes offer training in one or more of the five main areas listed above. In addition, a significant fraction of institutes offer training in laser systems, cryogenics, and RF for accelerators. This last part is particularly significant because it indicates a shift of training towards superconducting and laser based acceleration technologies.

Figure 6.2 : Percentage of institutes that offer training in each area.

The percentage of institutes that reported offering formal examinations on accelerator science coursework is shown by country and student type in Figure 6.3. In total, 22% of institutes that train undergraduates offer formal examinations; the corresponding Figure for master’s students is 37%, and for PhD students is 18%.

Figure 6.3: Percentage of institutes that offer formal examinations, by country.

In total, 18% of institutes that train undergraduates participate in European Credit Transfer Scheme (ECTS); the corresponding Figure for master’s students is 24% and that for PhD is 19%.

7. Accelerator Schools and the CERN Doctoral Student Programme

Accelerator schools represent an important training mechanism. The number of institutes which send people to accelerator schools by country is shown in Figure 7.1. The most attended international schools are the CERN Accelerator Schools (CAS), the Joint Universities Accelerator School (JUAS), the Nordic Particle Accelerator School (NPAS), the U.S. Particle Accelerator Schools (USPAS) and the Linear Collider School. CERN sends a significant number for training to the CAS. Poland sends a significant number for training at its WILGA school.

Figure 7.1: Number of institutes (universities and national/international laboratories) sending personnel to attend international and national accelerator schools, by country.

The number of companies which send people to accelerator schools is shown by country is shown in Figure 7.2. All the responding companies send their people to attend accelerator schools. The most attended international schools are the CERN Accelerator Schools (CAS), the Joint Universities Accelerator School (JUAS),

Figure 7.2: Number of companies sending personnel to attend international and national accelerator schools, by country.

In addition, the CERN Doctoral Student Programme (DSP) provides an important mechanism for the hands-on training of PhD students in accelerator science at CERN. Figure 7.3 shows participation in the CERN Doctoral Student Programme by country.

Figure 7.3: Numbers of trainees reported as participating in the CERN Doctoral Student Programme, by country

8. MOOC (Massive Open Online Course)

A massive open online course (MOOC) is an online course aimed at unlimited participation and open access via the web. It is a recent and widely researched development in distance education, which was first introduced in 2008 and emerged as a popular mode of learning in 2012.

The responding institutes have reported the following MOOCs related to training in accelerators.

1. Nordic particle accelerator project (NPAP) MOOC (<https://npap.eu/mooc/>)
2. An online course about particle accelerators, (<http://particle-accelerators.eu/>)
3. Cockcroft Institute Education Programme MOOC (<https://www.cockcroft.ac.uk/lectures>)
4. MOOC from Poland (<https://ekursy.okno.pw.edu.pl/>)
5. Russian MOOC

The target audience for NPAP MOOC is general students, students before undergraduate level and at the undergraduate level. The total duration of the NPAP MOOC is 41 hours. It is being used to train students in a university.

“An online course about particle accelerators” is being developed within the framework of the ARIES project. Its target duration is about 10 hours. Its target audience are the students at the end of the bachelor’s program or at the beginning of the master’s program

Cockcroft Institute Education Programme MOOC is developed for PhD level students. Its duration is 100 hours. It is used to train the PhD level students, who are based abroad.

The MOOC from Poland has 20 hours duration and it corresponds to 2 ECTs.

The Russian MOOC covers a wide range of students starting from general students, undergraduate students, master level students and doctoral students.

More information of the MOOCs can be found at the websites given above.

9. Training Materials and Use of Facilities

A number of standard text books are used in accelerator science training:

- An Introduction to Particle Accelerators (E. Wilson)
- An Introduction to the Physics of High Energy Accelerators (D.A. Edwards and M.J. Syphers)
- Beam instrumentation and diagnostics (P. Strehl)
- Fundamentals of Beam Physics (J. Rosenzweig)
- Handbook of Accelerator Physics and Engineering (A.W. Chao and M. Tigner)
- Measurement and control of charged particle beams (M.G. Minty and F. Zimmermann)
- Particle Accelerator Physics (H. Wiedemann)
- The Physics of Particle Accelerators (F. Hinterberger)
- The Physics of Particle Accelerators: an Introduction (K. Wille)
- R.F. Superconductivity (H. Padamsee)

Figure 9.1. The books are widely used for training all categories of trainee. Additional books and materials that were reported include:

- High Voltage Vacuum Insulation (R.V. Latham)
- The Physics and Technology of Ion Sources (Ian Brown)
- CAS Proceedings
- Biomedical particle accelerators (W. Scharf)
- Principles of Particle Accelerators (W.A. Benjamin)

Figure 9.1: Number of institutes using well known accelerator text books for training, by category of trainee.

73 institutes (81% of total) reported on their use of national and/or international laboratories and facilities for hands-on activities and visits as part of their training programs. A total of 51 such facilities were reported. Facilities used for training by two or more institutes are shown in Figure 9.2 .

Figure 9.2: Number of institutions using accelerator facilities for training, per facility

10. Past, Future Training activities and Training needs

Out of the 90 responding institutes, 4 universities and 1 company have reported on past training activities that have been stopped now. The reasons were decommissioning of facilities used for training (2 cases), and lack of students for small Universities (3 cases).

8 institutes among the 90 reporting institutes have planned future training activities in accelerator science. They include 7 universities and laboratories and one company.

Out of the 12 responding companies, 9 companies (81.8%) have expressed the need for additional training in accelerators, on top of the accelerator schools where they all send personnel.

The companies have indicated as training needs:

- Basic introductory training for new employees
- Constant updated retraining for the experts and engineers
- Some more expert courses for specific subjects
- Faster dissemination of the latest scientific findings
- A full university curriculum in Particle Accelerator Physics at the University.

11. Career Destinations

34 institutes provided information on career destinations for the different categories of accelerator science trainee. The percentages of each population moving into:

- postgraduate studies (relevant for undergraduates and master’s students)
- employment in the university sector
- employment at national or international laboratories
- employment in the manufacturing sector
- employment in the financial sector (e.g. banking)
- employment in the services sector (e.g. information technology)

are shown in Figure 11.1. For example, 29% of the undergraduates, and 26% of the master’s students, go on to pursue postgraduate training. 24% of the PhD students, and 24% of the postdoctoral fellows, go on to find employment at universities and national or international laboratories. 15% of undergraduates, 20% of masters, 24% of PhDs, 21% post-doctoral fellows, 20% of staff joins National/International laboratories. For each category of trainee, significant numbers go on to find employment outside the academic research sector: 37% of the undergraduates, 41% of the master’s students, 42% of the PhD students, 41% of the postdoctoral fellows and 37% of staff find employment in the manufacturing, financial and services sectors.

Figure 11.1: Percentage of trainees by career destination for each category of trainee.

12. Conclusions and Recommendations

This survey has given a broad overview of training activities in accelerator science in Europe, and some indications on how they could evolve to take into account the needs of accelerator laboratories and companies. The overall response rate to the survey was 61% for universities and scientific laboratories, and 92% for companies. Globally, the sample gives a good representation of the European particle accelerator community, and particularly of the companies active in particle accelerator research.

The main conclusion of this study is that accelerator training is widely performed by a large and diverse number of institutions, well integrated between them and with the laboratories operating particle accelerators. As could be expected, the main providers of training are Universities, with as many as 39 universities providing some training, and 34 out of them offering formal lectures on accelerators. While almost all national and international laboratories organise some sort of training, organised internal training is used only by a small fraction of companies.

The diversification and integration of the training offer within the accelerator community is demonstrated by the large number of training instruments beyond formal lectures. Practically all institutes and companies contacted send people to attend Accelerator Schools organised by laboratories or laboratory consortia, taking place in a different country from where the persons are located, and almost all laboratories and a large fraction of universities and companies send people to International Workshops and Conferences. Hands-on training at accelerator facilities is also a privileged training scheme, followed by about 40% of all respondents to the survey. While MOOC's are starting to be used for training, it is interesting to notice that only companies use online training material.

In terms of numbers, training in accelerator science reaches about 1,200 people per year, a large number when compared to a community of about 5,000 people estimated to work on accelerator construction and R&D activities in Europe. While as expected the largest share is represented by university students, many training activities occur outside of universities, organised by laboratories for their post-doctoral fellows and staff members, and usually open to outside participants.

Training in accelerator is not evenly distributed across Europe: Germany and the United Kingdom are the countries providing more formal training in accelerator science, in particular to PhD students, followed by Finland, Poland and Italy (for master students).

The two main Accelerator Schools periodically organised in Europe have achieved a strong reputation and a broad attendance, reaching a large number of students from 48 (CERN Accelerator School, 2016/19) and 28 (JUAS, 2017/20) different countries.

From companies comes a strong demand for more formal training opportunities for their staff, beyond the usual channel of accelerator schools. In particular, they call for some basic introductory training for new employees and constant updated retraining for their staff.

It is interesting to observe that training in accelerator science profits at the society as large because more than one out of three of trainees in accelerators at all levels find an employment in the

manufacturing, financial and service sectors. One out of four of all PhD's and Post-docs find an employment in a national or international laboratory.

This analysis leads to identifying some possible actions to improve accelerator training meeting the interests of the community at large, and in particular of its industrial part:

- Favour movement of students within countries and across Europe to reach critical mass for university courses on accelerators.
- Support the European Accelerator Schools as primary tools for training and integration of the accelerator community.
- Organise general and specialised courses for industry personnel.
- Spread training initiatives beyond the usual high-technology countries (e.g. Germany and UK).
- Continue the development of MOOC courses and integrate the requirements of accelerator companies in the preparation of online training material.
- Organize outreach activities at bachelor level or even at high school level, to develop early interest in acceleration technologies among the students.
- Enhance the dissemination of latest accelerator related results and findings, in particular to industry, via web-based bulletins like the existing Accelerating News.

APPENDIX 1

RESPONDING INSTITUTES

Country	Institute
Austria	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology
Belgium	IBA (Ion Beam Applications) SCK/CEN
Czech Republic	ELI Beamlines
Denmark	ISA Aarhus University
Denmark	Danfysik
Finland	Aalto University
Finland	Åbo Akademi University
Finland	Department of Physics University of Jyväskylä
France	CNRS
France	CEA
France	Université Paris-Saclay
France	Université de Grenoble
France	Université de Nantes
France	SOLEIL
France	Sigmaphi
Germany	DELTA TU Dortmund
Germany	FEP (Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft)
Germany	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
Germany	Institut für Kernphysik der Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz
Germany	Institut für Kernphysik FZ Jülich
Germany	TU Darmstadt
Germany	University of Frankfurt
Germany	University of Mainz
Germany	University of Siegen
Germany	University of Wuppertal
Germany	Research Instruments
Germany	BHTS (Bruker HTS)
Hungary	Wigner RCP
Italy	INFN - Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati
Italy	INFN - Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati
Italy	INFN - Napoli & Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II
Italy	Sincrotrone Trieste

Latvia	Riga Technical University
Malta	UoM
Norway	University of Oslo
Poland	National Centre for Nuclear Research
Poland	Warsaw University of Technology
Poland	Wrocław University of Science and Technology
Poland	IFJ PAN
Portugal	CERN
Russia	National Research Nuclear University -Moscow Engineering Physics Institute
Slovakia	IEE
Slovenia	COSYLAB
Spain	ALBA CELLS
Spain	Elytt Energy
Sweden	European Spallation Source ESS ERIC
Sweden	Stockholm University
Sweden	Lund University
Sweden	Uppsala University
Sweden	(INDUSTRY) General Electric Healthcare
Switzerland	EPFL: Swiss Institute of Technology Lausanne
Switzerland	CERN
United Kingdom	Diamond Light Source
United Kingdom	Glasgow University
United Kingdom	Huddersfield University
United Kingdom	John Adams Institute Royal Holloway University of London
United Kingdom	John Adams Institute University of Oxford
United Kingdom	Lancaster University
United Kingdom	Liverpool University
United Kingdom	Manchester University
United Kingdom	Science and Technology Facilities Council
United Kingdom	Strathclyde University
United Kingdom	Surrey University
United Kingdom	University College London
United Kingdom	Warwick University
United Kingdom	UKRI STFC Daresbury Laboratory
United Kingdom	University of Glasgow

APPENDIX 2

The survey was a web based survey. A text version is given below.

GDPR acceptance and consent to ESS

You & Your Institution

Your Name

Your institution

Country

Type of institution

(University /National Laboratory / Company/ Other)

Yes / No questions on Type of Training

Does your institute offers training in accelerators presently ? (Yes/ No)

(if “No” to above)

Have you offered training in accelerator science in the past? (Yes/No)

Do you plan to offer training in the future? (Yes/No)

(if “No” to above)

Would it be desirable to offer such training? (Yes/No)

Even if your institution does not provide training in accelerator science, do any of your faculty members provide training in accelerator science at other institutions or workshops? (Yes/No)

Do you send any people to accelerator schools and workshops? (Yes/No)

Training

To which groups do you offer training? (Undergraduates/Master’s-level students/PhD students/Post-doctoral fellows (not permanent appointments/Staff (permanent appointments)/Others)

Students (this section is repeated for each of the student types selected above)

In which areas do you provide training? (Particle sources/Accelerating structures/Magnets/Beam dynamics/Beam instrumentation and control/Laser systems for accelerators/Cryogenics)

Other training areas (please specify)

Names of training programs

How many students received training in academic year 2018/19?

How many students will receive training in academic year 2019/20?

Approximately how many students PER YEAR received training, averaged over the 5 years 2013-2017?

Teaching

How many hours of lectures or other formal training (in accelerator science) did the students receive in 2018/19? (e.g. 100)

What is the total number of hours of instruction (in all subjects) during the academic year? (e.g. 500)

Do you participate in the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System scheme? (Yes/No/Don't know)

If applicable, how many ECTS credits does your accelerator training amount to?

Are there formal examinations in accelerator science? (Yes/No)

Which books do you use for teaching?

An Introduction to Particle Accelerators (E. Wilson)

An Introduction to the Physics of High Energy Accelerators (D.A. Edwards and M.J. Syphers)

Beam instrumentation and diagnostics (P. Strehl)

Fundamentals of Beam Physics (J. Rosenzweig)

Handbook of Accelerator Physics and Engineering (A.W. Chao and M. Tigner)

Measurement and control of charged particle beams (M.G. Minty and F. Zimmermann)

Particle Accelerator Physics (H. Wiedemann)

Physik der Teilchenbeschleuniger (F. Hinterberger)

The Physics of Particle Accelerators: an Introduction (K. Wille)

Other books (please specify)

Do you use local, national or international accelerator facilities for 'hands-on' training? (Yes/No)

(if "Yes" above)

Which facilities?

Faculty

Do your faculty members provide accelerator training at other institutions? (e.g. national laboratories or other universities) (*Yes/No*)

(if “Yes” above)

Which other institutions?

Do your faculty members provide training at any accelerator schools? (*Yes/No*)

(if “Yes” above)

Which accelerator schools?

Doctoral Training Programmes

Do you participate in any CERN doctoral training programmes? (*Yes/No*)

(if “Yes” above)

How many students joined the programme in academic year 2018/19?

How many students do you expect to join in academic year 2019/20?

How many students joined per year, averaged over the 5 years 2013-2017? (approximate)

If you participate in other doctoral Training Programmes (please give information)

Accelerator Schools

To which accelerator school do you send people to ?

CERN Accelerator School

Joint Universities Accelerator School

United States Particle Accelerator School

Linear Collider School

Other accelerator schools

(If “Other accelerator schools” is ticked above)

Which other accelerator schools?

MOOC

Has your institute developed MOOC ? (Yes/No)

If yes,

target audience of the MOOC / duration of MOOC / ECTs corresponding to the MOOC / whether any university is using MOOC for teaching /

Past Training Activities

Are your past training activities are stopped now (yes/no)

if yes,

(from which year were the activities offered / when did they stop /what were the training activities / reason for stopping the activities /)

can the stopped activities be continued –

if yes, do you need any resources to continue

if yes what resources do you need

Future Training Activities

Has your institute planned any future training activity (yes/ no)

If yes, give information about the planned activity if you need additional resources, give information

Career Destinations

Please provide information on the career destinations of your leavers in the following categories, averaged over the 5 years 2013-2017 (if known).

(repeated for each student type)

Postgraduate studies (or “University sector” for postgraduate alumni) National

and international laboratories

Manufacturing sector

Financial sector (e.g. banks)

Service sector (e.g. IT)

APPENDIX 3

CAS STATISTICS

The CERN Accelerator School holds training courses for physicists and engineers. The number of general courses per year were two till 2010, and has been increased recently to 4 courses/year in 2018 and 3 courses/year in 2019.

The courses take place in conference centers in different member states of CERN and consist of a program of lectures and tutorials spread over a period of two weeks. Participants are welcome from member states of CERN and other countries world-wide.

More details can be found at <https://cas.web.cern.ch/cas/>. A summary of the CAS student institute national affiliations, and student nationalities, is given in the table below.

Sr.No.	Countries	Attendees during 2016			Attendees during 2017			Attendees during 2018			Attendees during 2019		
		Participants	Grant	lecturers									
1	Austria				4			6			4		
2	Australia	1										2	
3	Armenia								1			2	
4	Belarus												1
5	Belgium	2						1			1		
6	Canada				3			1			3		
7	Brazil											2	
8	Bulgaria												
9	China	1			13	1		9	4		2	1	
10	Czech Republic	1			2			1			1		
11	Denmark												1
12	Finland							3		2			
13	France	5	1		16		1	27	4	1	30	1	3
14	German	12	1	3	23	1	9	36	4	12	30	4	7
15	Greece												
16	Hungary	2				1							
17	India							1	1			6	
18	Indonesia								1			1	
19	Israel										2	1	1
20	Iran					3		2	6				
21	Italy	3		2	7	2	6	5	2	6	8	3	3
22	Japan				2					3	1		2
23	Jordan				1								
24	Latvia											1	
25	Mexico				1				1				
26	Netherlands												
27	Norway												
28	Poland	3						3					
29	Portugal										12	1	4
30	Russia	2			7	3		7	9	2	4	4	1
31	Romania	1						2		4	2		
33	Slovenia							4			4		
34	Spain	5			4			3			2		
35	Sweden	4		1	10		4	5	1	1	3		1
36	Switzerland	65		13	202		53	165			83		58
37	Turkey				1								
38	United Kingdom	8		4	15		6	13		6	24	3	8
39	South africa	2						1				1	
40	turkey		2					1	1				
41	Thailand							1	1		0	1	
42	Tunis										1		
43	ukrane		1						2			1	
44	United states	1			3			1	1	7	6	2	4
45	Madagascar								1				
46	Malta							1					
47	Zimbabwe									1			
48	Saudi arabia										1		

Comparison Graph for average attendees averaged per year during 2006-2010 and 2013-2019 is shown below.

The large number of students from Switzerland is due to the presence of CERN and all the CERN students as counted as Switzerland students. The increase in the average attendees per year observed during 2017-2019 is due to the increase in the number of courses per year.

APPENDIX 4

JUAS STATISTICS

The Joint Universities Accelerator School holds training courses for Master students, PhD students and engineers once per year. The courses take place in the “Centre Universitaire”-Archamps (Haute-Savoie) in France, 15km from CERN. They consist of a programme of lectures and tutorials spread over a period of 10 weeks. Participants are welcome from European universities, European Institutes and other countries world-wide.

The first course “Sciences & Physics of Particle Accelerators” runs, each year, at the beginning of January followed by the second one “Technology & Applications of Particle Accelerators”. Students could present examinations at the end of each course and could obtain a total of 20 ECTS (European Credit Transfer System) credits, recognised by the 14 European university partners of JUAS.

The first figure below shows universities students who have followed JUAS courses between 2017 and 2020; the second figure shows the average number of students coming from the various European laboratories and institutes for the same period.

The JUAS web site at <http://cern.ch/juas> provides more details.

SR no	Countries	Year			
		2017	2018	2019	2020
1	Austria	1	1	1	1
2	Belgium	5	2	0	0
3	China	1	0	2	0
4	Czech Republ	0	0	1	0
5	Denmark	0	2	0	0
6	Finland	1	0	0	0
7	France	18	21	21	15
8	Germany	5	7	1	4
9	Greece	2	4	3	0
10	Hungary	1	0	1	0
11	India	1	0	1	0
12	Iran	1	0	0	0
13	Italy	9	9	10	19
14	Jordan	0	2	1	0
15	Mexico	0	1	0	0
16	Norway	1	0	0	0
17	Pakistan	0	0	3	0
18	Poland	1	1	0	1
19	Russia	0	0	1	1
20	Romania	4	0	0	0
21	Saudi Arabia	0	0	1	0
22	Spain	1	2	2	0
23	Sweden	1	0	3	3
24	Switzerland	8	4	7	3
25	USA	0	0	0	1
26	Turkey	1	0	1	1
27	Ukraine	1	1	0	0
28	UK	2	2	0	0
total		65	59	60	49

JUAS Course-1 attendance				
Year	Masters	Doctoral	Professional	Total
2016	12	22	6	
2017	13	19	5	40
2018	13	13	3	37
2019	13	9	5	29
2020	11	10	1	27

JUAS Course-2 attendance				
Year	Masters	Doctoral	Professional	Total
2016	22	9	17	
2017	17	11	14	48
2018	15	8	14	42
2019	18	12	12	37
2020	24	4	5	42

